

INNOVATIVE SUSTAINABLE COMPOSITES FOR LIGHTER AND FLAME RETARDANT ELECTRIC VEHICLE PARTS TO BOOST CLIMATE BENEFITS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated novel, lightweight, and sustainable flame-retardant biocomposites of polyamide 6 (PA6) and waste-derived biocarbon for electric vehicle (EV) parts to address EV challenges and promote sustainable waste management. Agricultural wheat straw and mixed paper-plastic wastes underwent pyrolysis at 600 °C, and the resulting biocarbons were employed as reinforcements at 20 and 30 wt% loading in the PA 6 matrix through melt extrusion. The mechanical and flammability characteristics of these biocarbon-loaded PA 6 composites were compared with those of 20 wt% polyurethane-treated recycled carbon fiber (PurCF) reinforced polyamide 6,6 (PA6,6) composites developed by Olonisakin et al. [1]. The morphological analysis revealed that biocarbon particles showed significant adherence and integration within the polyamide matrix, although oriented randomly, indicating a robust interfacial bond between the biocarbon particles and the polyamide matrix. The incorporation of biocarbon effectively improved the mechanical performance of the corresponding biocomposites. The heat distortion temperature (HDT) of neat PA increased from 120.8 °C to 182.4 °C and 186.3 °C with the addition of 30 wt% WSB and PPB, respectively. The inclusion of biocarbon into neat PA 6 increased the overall flame duration of composites during the vertical burning test, except for 20PPB, achieving a UL-94 V-2 rating. During the horizontal burning test, all samples demonstrated a linear burning rate of 0 mm/min, which can be attributed to the intumescent behaviour of biocarbon composites. The PA 6,6 composites exhibited higher mechanical properties compared to PA 6 composites, but inferior flame retardancy compared to PA 6 composites. The developed lightweight, sustainable PA 6 biocomposites with reduced flammability and boosted mechanical, rheological and thermal performance could potentially be applied to develop EV parts.

1 INTRODUCTION

The rapid rise in the automotive sector, particularly in electric vehicles (EVs), has intensified the need for lightweight, robust, non-flammable, and environmentally friendly materials to enhance fuel efficiency and mitigate greenhouse gas emissions. Polymer composites have garnered considerable attention among innovative materials due to their beneficial characteristics [2]. Polyamide 6 (PA6) is a prevalent engineering thermoplastic in the automobile industry, recognised for its remarkable tensile

properties, chemical resistance, and heat stability [3]. To improve its characteristics or alleviate its drawbacks, many fillers have been included in polyamide, either alone or in combination. Glass and carbon-based mineral fillers are commonly employed for their exceptional thermal stability and ability to endure the high processing temperatures of PA 6, which may exceed 290 °C [3]. However, these fillers often pose difficulties, as they may be costly, unwieldy, or environmentally detrimental. Advanced fillers such as carbon fibre, carbon nanotubes, and graphene possess great density and are significantly expensive due to their complex and costly production methods. Meanwhile, materials like talc, nanoclay, and glass fibre offer a cost-effective alternative, but they are characterised by their notably high densities. The aforementioned fillers are also unsustainable due to their derivation from petroleum-based materials or the exhaustion of natural resources. The performance of PA6 can be further improved by integrating appropriate fillers or reinforcements. The primary utilisation of petroleum-derived fillers prompts environmental and economic issues, requiring a transition to renewable and bio-based substitutes [4–6].

Biomass-derived biocarbon or biochar, a carbon-rich material generated via pyrolysis of renewable biomass sources like agricultural residues, forestry by-products, or organic waste, has been recognised as a potential reinforcement in polyamide composites. Biocarbon reduces reliance on fossil resources and offers a sustainable approach to waste management [7]. The unique properties of low density render it an appealing filler material for the development of eco-friendly composites [8]. Moreover, it is generally more cost-effective than nearly all carbon-based fillers and exhibits a lower density, which ranges from 1.34 to 1.96 g/cm³ [8]. Biocarbon is a highly complex material. The characteristics, especially the surface chemistry, may vary considerably depending on the initial chemical composition and the processing conditions. The proportions and types of functionalities can vary significantly and are largely dependent on the pyrolysis temperature [9]. As a result of its polar characteristics, biocarbon exhibits a significant affinity for polymers of similar polarity, such as PA 6. Researchers examined various biomass-derived biocarbon sources, such as wood, miscanthus, corn cob and lignin, as sustainable reinforcing fillers for PA6 [3,5,9].

The conversion of biomass and waste materials into valuable products reduces environmental impacts and increases economic value [10]. Canada's annual production of wheat straw is estimated at 21 million tonnes [11]. Kalak indicated that approximately 360 million tonnes of biomass, specifically straw, are utilised worldwide. The applications include the pulp and paper industry, furniture and building materials, agriculture for animal feed and bedding, and the energy sector. The accessibility, affordability, and renewable nature of wheat straw make it a valuable resource for biocarbon production [12]. Research indicates that biochar derived from wheat straw can serve as a fertiliser for sustainable agricultural practices and in thermal energy storage applications. Compared to wheat straw, plastics are among the most widely used materials in various applications on a daily basis. The volume of plastic waste has significantly increased in recent years [13]. The pyrolysis of mixed plastic-paper waste into biocarbon for polymers has the potential to mitigate various environmental challenges and play a substantial role in advancing the circular economy. Biocarbon derived from waste demonstrates greater stability compared to raw biomass or waste, thereby presenting considerable potential as a reinforcing filler for sustainable polymer composites. There is a notable deficiency in research regarding the utilisation of both wheat straw and plastic-paper waste pyrolysed biocarbon in sustainable polymer composite applications, indicating a necessity for further investigation.

The primary aim of this research work is to develop waste-derived biocarbon reinforced PA6 sustainable composites with reduced flammability for automotive applications, especially for EV parts. The wheat straw and mixed paper-plastic waste were subjected to pyrolysis at a constant temperature of 600 °C, followed by ball milling for 2 hours before integration into the polymer matrix. For the first time, PA6 sustainable composites containing 20 and 30 wt% of this biocarbon were assessed in terms of physico-mechanical, thermal, rheological, and flame-retardant properties. Finally, the mechanical and flammability properties of PA6 biocomposites were compared with those of 20 wt% polyurethane-treated recycled carbon fiber (PurCF) reinforced polyamide 6,6 (PA6,6) composites developed by Olonisakin et al. [1].

2 EXPERIMENTAL, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1 Materials

Polyamide 6 (PA6): Ultramid B27E was provided by BASF. This particular grade of PA 6 has been identified by a density of 1.12–1.15 g/cm³, melting point of 220 °C and melt flow index: MFI_(250 °C, 2.16 kg) of 38 g/10 min. The plastic and paper waste, having approximately 20w/80w composition, was collected from the University of Guelph, Canada campus. The wheat straw was purchased from Salem Creek Farms, 2408 Concession 4, Teeswater, Canada.

2.2 Pyrolysis of wheat straw and paper-plastic waste

The pyrolysis process of wheat straw and paper-plastic waste was performed by employing a laboratory-scale pyrolysis reactor at 600 °C to produce biocarbon. All the raw waste and biomass materials were dried for at least 24 hours prior to the pyrolysis process to get a moisture content of less than 5%. To conduct the pyrolysis process, a Carbolite GLO 10/11-1G front-loading retort furnace (UK) configured in a horizontal orientation was used. About 1000 g of each raw material was put into the furnace using a steel vessel, subsequently, the atmosphere was rendered inert by flushing with nitrogen gas. A heating rate of 7.5 °C/min was utilized to attain the target performing temperature of 600 °C, upheld for a residence duration of 1 hour prior to cooling the furnace to ambient temperature for biocarbon removal for all three cases. The biocarbons were subsequently subjected to ball milling at a rotational speed of 200 rpm for 2 hours for each biocarbon sample. The overall yield of the wheat straw and paper-plastic biocarbon was 34 and 24.4%, respectively. The above-mentioned two biocarbons are designated as WSB and PPB, respectively.

2.3 Processing of PA 6 sustainable biocomposites

In order to prevent void formation and hydrolysis during the melt-extrusion process, the biocarbon and PA 6 were dried before to the processing step. Melt-extrusion was performed to make neat PA 6 and its sustainable biocomposites in a DSM Micro Xplore 15cc, Netherlands twin-screw micro-compounder for a duration of two minutes at a temperature of 250 degrees Celsius and a rotor speed of one hundred revolutions per minute. For the purpose of producing tensile dumbbell-shaped, flexural bars, and impact bars specimens in accordance with the parameters of ASTM standards, the molten polymer was first collected in a transfer device and then injected into an injection moulding machine, Micro 12cc, Netherlands. The temperature of the machine was set to 30 degrees Celsius. Prior to the testing, each sample was conditioned for a period of forty-eight hours at a humidity level of fifty percent at room temperature. Sustainable composites with both 20 and 30 wt% of each biocarbon were fabricated and designated as shown in Table 1.

Sample designation	PA 6 (wt%)	Paint char (wt%)	Wheat straw biocarbon (wt%)	Paper-plastic biocarbon (wt%)
PA6	100	0	0	0
20WSB	80	0	20	0
20PPB	80	0	0	20
30WSB	70	0	30	0
30PPB	70	0	0	30

Table 1: Compositions for PA 6 composites containing 20 and 30 wt% biocarbon

2.4 Characterizations

Using the FEI Quanta FEG 250 machine and an accelerating voltage of 20 kV, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to examine the biocarbon dispersion in the PA6 matrix. The Denton Desk

V TSC sputter coater was used to gold sputter the broken surface of impact samples, with a 90-second coating period. Using the Melt Flow Indexer Qualitest 2000A in accordance with ASTM D1238, the MFI of the clean PA 6 and all sustainable composites was calculated at 250 °C with a constant load of 2.16 kg [14]. The MD-300S Densitometer (Alfa Mirage, Japan) was used to quantify the density of each specimen. In accordance with ASTM D638-14 for the tensile test at a speed of 50 mm/min for neat PA 6 and 5 mm/min for sustainable composites, and ASTM D790-10 for the flexural testing at a rate of 14 mm/min, the mechanical analysis was carried out using an Instron Universal Testing Machine (3382, MA, USA) [15,16]. Using a 2.75 J impact pendulum and the Zwick/Roell Hit25P (Ulm, Germany), the Izod notched impact test was conducted in accordance with ASTM D256 standard (test method A) [17]. Using the Q800 dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA), the heat deflection temperature (HDT) was measured in accordance with the technical note from TA Instruments (DE, USA). Samples loaded in the three-point clamp of the instrument were heated to 250 °C with a heating rate of 2 °C/min under a force of 0.455 MPa until a deflection of 250 µm was achieved. For the composite of 20 wt% PurCF loaded PA 6,6 (PurCF20) used here to compare the results with PA 6 composites, a force of 1.8 MPa was used to measure the HDT value [1]. The flame-retardant properties of neat polyamide and its sustainable biocomposites were tested in accordance with ASTM D635-22 [34]. The vertical flammability test was performed in accordance with ASTM D3801-20a for five specimens of comparable lengths [18]. The classification of the samples was established based on the observed after-flame and after-glow durations, as well as dripping and cotton ignition during the testing process [19].

2.5 Results and discussion

2.5.1 Density and melt flow index (MFI)

Because they have such a large impact on the vehicle's total weight and fuel efficiency, low-density polymers and composites are ideal for use in automobiles [1]. The measured density of neat PA 6 and its sustainable biocomposites with two different types of biocarbon are provided in Table 2. Virgin PA 6 exhibited a density of 1.105 g/cm³. The addition of 20 and 30 wt% of biocarbon increased the density of the resultant PA 6 composites. The density of 20 wt% PurCF-filled PA 6,6 composites was found to be higher compared to PA 6 composites with 20 wt% biocarbon but lower than those with 30 wt% biocarbon [1]. The preferred MFI of composite materials for the injection molding process should be greater than 10 g/min to achieve better processability and thereby cost and output efficiencies. **Table 2** also provides the MFI of neat PA 6 and all sustainable composites loaded with 20 and 30 wt% biocarbon, as well as PA 6,6 composite (PurCF20). It can be seen that neat PA 6 exhibited an MFI of 39.6 g/10 min, which decreased with the incorporation of carbonaceous filler such as biocarbon particles in the neat PA matrix. The incorporation of biocarbon raised the viscosity of the melt due to PA 6 chain tangling and the high aspect ratio of biocarbon promotes strong adhesion between the carbonaceous fillers and the PA matrix phase. The PPB composites exhibited a higher MFI value compared to that of the WSB composites. The reduction of the MFI of polyamide with biocarbon inclusion was extensively studied and reported in the literature [5,9]. The PA 6,6 composites exhibited higher MFI compared to PA 6 composites owing to the high MFI value of neat PA 6,6 [1].

Sample designation	Density (g/cm ³)	MFI (g/10 min)
PA 6	1.105±0.003	39.6±1.2
20WSB	1.154±0.001	21.0±0.53
20PPB	1.150±0.002	27.46±0.50
30WSB	1.197±0.005	13.7±0.41
30PPB	1.191±0.001	17.8±0.72
20rCF	1.18 ± 0.003	106.38±1.24

Table 2: Density and MFI of neat PA 6, PA 6 biocomposites and PA 6,6 composites

2.5.2 Morphological analysis

The biocarbon dispersion in the neat polyamide matrix was investigated by SEM analysis of the impact-fractured composite samples. Figure 1(a) and (b) represent the SEM images of impact fracture surfaces of PA 6 sustainable biocomposites loaded with 20 wt% of wheat straw and paper-plastic biocarbon, respectively, whereas the surface morphology of 30 wt% biocarbon-filled composites is represented in Figure 1(c) and (d). Several biocarbon particles identified on the fracture surface of all composites were noted, showing no signs of dislodgement or significant pullouts. The biocarbon particles demonstrated significant adherence and integration within the polyamide matrix, indicating effective interfacial adhesion. The platelet-shaped WSB and PPB particles are uniformly distributed within the polyamide matrix, although they exhibit a random orientation at both 20 and 30 wt% filler loading. The surface properties of biocarbon particles improved interfacial interactions with polar PA 6 chains.

2.5.3 Mechanical properties

The effect of carbonaceous filler types and concentration in PA 6 on the mechanical properties, HDT and flame retardancy was investigated and the obtained results are depicted in Figure 2. The mechanical, HDT and flammability properties of 20 wt% PurCF loaded PA 6,6 composites were also provided in Figure 2 for comparison [1]. The variation of tensile strength and modulus for polyamide composites loaded with 20 and 30 wt% biocarbon as well as PA 6,6 composites, is shown in Figure 2(a). Virgin PA 6 possessed a tensile strength and tensile modulus of 73 MPa and 2693 MPa, respectively. The incorporation of 20 wt% biocarbon enhanced tensile strength, particularly tensile modulus, relative to unmodified polyamide, and these attributes were further augmented by 30 wt% char and biocarbon-reinforced composites. This phenomenon is ascribed to the stiffening effect of high modulus filler particles, which are typically more rigid than the polymer matrix. A 34.3% and 36.8% increase in tensile modulus was achieved for the PA 6 composites using 30 wt% wheat straw and paper-plastic biocarbon, respectively, in comparison to the pure polymer. The flexural strength and flexural modulus of PA 6 were markedly enhanced with biocarbon loading, as illustrated in Figure 2(b). Both the flexural strength and modulus consistently exhibited greater values for 30 wt% biocarbon composites in comparison to those with 20 wt% filler loading. The rapid and effective transmission of stress from the polyamide to the char and biocarbon in tension mode, coupled with the confinement of the PA molecular chains by the biocarbon in compression mode, resulted in a significant improvement in flexural characteristics [5]. From both Figure 2(a) and (b), it was noted that 20 wt% PurCF-reinforced PA 6,6 composites demonstrated remarkably high tensile and flexural strength, as well as moduli, in comparison to PA 6 composites. This can be attributed to the fundamental characteristics of carbon fibre, including its stiffness, high strength, and modulus [1]. The variation in the notched impact strength of neat PA 6 and its sustainable biocarbon, as well as PA 6,6 composites, is provided in Figure 2(c). An impact strength of 57.9 J/m was achieved for neat PA 6, which decreased continually with filler loading. With 20 wt% of carbonaceous filler loading, the impact strength of neat polyamide was reduced to 35.6 and 33.7 J/m for WSB and PPB, respectively. The incorporation of reinforcing fillers significantly reduces the ductility of the composite material blend. The impact strength was further decreased with 30 wt% filler concentration in the polyamide matrix. The presence of invasive biocarbon particles may create vulnerabilities within the matrix, thus promoting crack propagation [20]. The PurCF20 composite exhibited an impact strength of 38 J/m, that is slightly higher than that for 20 wt% biocarbon-loaded PA 6 composites [1].

Figure 1: SEM micrographs of PA 6 biocomposites filled with (a) 20 wt% wheat straw biocarbon, (b) 20 wt% paper-plastic biocarbon, (c) 30 wt% wheat straw biocarbon and (d) 30 wt% paper-plastic biocarbon.

2.5.4 Heat deflection temperature (HDT)

HDT is a critical attribute of engineering thermoplastics, particularly in the automotive sector, as it establishes temperature thresholds for material processing [3]. HDT reflects a material's resistance to heat under a specified load. The HDT of virgin polyamide 6 composites and PA 6,6 composite (PurCF20) are plotted in Figure 2(c). The HDT value of neat PA 6 was 121 °C, which was markedly enhanced by the incorporation of 20 wt% char and biocarbon in the matrix phase. When the biocarbon concentration in the PA matrix was increased from 20 to 30 wt%, the HDT of the corresponding composites increased further. The HDT of neat PA increased to 182.4 °C and 186.3 °C with 30 wt% WSB and PPB loading. The thermally stable biocarbon particles restricted the movement of polyamide chains, limiting the composite deformation by raising the temperature required to deform the composite materials [5]. Hence, HDT improved significantly for biocarbon composites. The higher carbonaceous content of WSB and PPB compared to PCB contributed to the greater HDT value of the corresponding composites, attributed to the boosted stiffness and rigidity of the filler particles of denser structure. The PA 6,6 composite with 20 wt% PurCF exhibited a higher HDT value of 242.9 °C measured at a force of 1.8 MPa [1].

Figure 2: (a) Tensile strength and modulus, (b) flexural strength and modulus, (c) impact strength and HDT, and (d) flammability behavior in the UL-94 vertical (total flame time) and horizontal burning (linear burning rate) tests of PA 6 composites and PA 6,6 composite [1].

2.5.5 Flammability characteristics

A critical characteristic of materials utilised in the automotive sector, particularly in electric vehicle components, is their flame resistance. For these applications, the materials must demonstrate minimum flammability to the highest degree feasible [21]. The UL-94 vertical and horizontal flammability tests are among the most used methods employed to assess the flame retardancy of polymer composites. The reaction of pure PA 6 and biocarbon-infused composites to flame exposure was documented as total flame duration for five samples in the vertical test and linear burning rate in the horizontal experiment. The outcomes for PA 6 composites and PurCF PA 6,6 sustainable composites are illustrated in Figure 2(d). The incorporation of 20 wt% WSB biocarbon particles into the PA 6 matrix extended the total flame duration to 117.4 seconds. The 20PPB composite demonstrated a flame time of 59.9 seconds, which is less than that of neat polyamide. The PA 6,6 composites demonstrated a total flame duration of 212.8 seconds, surpassing that of PA 6 composites. All composites demonstrated a UL-94 V-2 classification in the vertical test. The improved fire retardancy of paper-plastic biocarbon-loaded composites is due to the emergence of a more efficient protective carbon layer resulting from the more ordered and crystalline carbon structure of PPB particles. In the horizontal burning test, both the pure polymer and composites exhibited a burning rate of 0 mm/min and were categorised as HB, as illustrated in Figure 2(d). None of the samples exceeded the 25 mm reference point, and the flame extinguished. The thermally stable carbon structure of the filler and the little nitrogen content in the filler particles resulted in intumescent behaviour when positioned horizontally. Muir et al. investigated and reported the diminished flame retardancy of recycled PA 6 infused with lignin biocarbon pyrolysed at various temperatures [22]. The PurCF20 composites showed a linear burning rate of 22.16 mm/min in the horizontal flammability test [1]. Therefore, biocarbon-loaded PA 6 composites exhibited higher flame retardancy compared to PurCF-loaded PA 6,6 composites owing to the formation of more effective char layers by biocarbon particles than carbon fibers.

3 CONCLUSIONS

This research investigated the effect of wheat straw and mixed paper-plastics derived biocarbon on the characteristics and performance of PA 6 sustainable composites intended for automotive applications, especially in EVs. The impact of 20 and 30 wt% biocarbon (pyrolyzed at 600 °C) concentration on the thermomechanical, rheological, and flammability qualities of PA biocomposites was assessed and compared with 20 wt% polyurethane-treated CF-loaded PA 6,6 composites published by Olonisakin et al. [1]. The addition of biocarbon significantly improved tensile/flexural strength and moduli in comparison to neat PA 6. The HDT increased to 186 °C for 30PPB composites and consistently remained higher for all biocarbon composites than the neat polyamide. The integration of biocarbon extended the overall flaming duration of biocomposites to neat polyamide in the vertical burning test. Although the 20PPB composite demonstrated a shorter flame duration compared to neat PA 6, all composites, along with neat polyamide, were categorized as V-2, demonstrating dripping and ignition of cotton. In the horizontal burning test, all samples exhibited a linear burning rate of 0 mm/min, attributed to the intumescent behavior of char and biocarbon composites. The PA 6,6 exhibited higher mechanical properties compared to PA 6 composites, but inferior flame retardancy compared to PA 6 composites.

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